

The First English Publication of Mendeleev's Periodic Table

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Abstract

This paper traces the earliest appearance of Mendeleev's periodic table in an English publication, showing that the table first reached the Anglophone world through a major reference work—unlike the German case, where it arrived via a journal abstract.

In my search for the very first appearance of Mendeleev's periodic table in an English publication, credit must go to Stephen G. Brush's seminal article *The Reception of Mendeleev's Periodic Law in America and Britain*.¹ Yet not mentioned by Brush, I stumbled upon a strong candidate while examining the earliest entries he provided.

Among the first papers listed by Brush that mention the periodic law,² only one reproduces Mendeleev's table: *Remarks in connection with the discovery of gallium*—by Mendeleev himself and dated December 24, 1875—in which the recently discovered metal is identified as the predicted eka-aluminium.

As for the books, leaving aside the one by Gustavus Hinrichs in 1874³ for not including the table, Brush lists two of 1877 that do describe it, namely: Ira Remsen's *Principles of Theoretical Chemistry*, and Thomas Thorpe's *Manual of Inorganic Chemistry, vol. II: The Metals*. While Remsen refers the reader to the German translations of Mendeleev's canonical papers,⁴ Thorpe adds another reference: the *Second Supplement* to Henry Watts's *Dictionary of Chemistry and the Allied Branches of Other Sciences*.

Since so many nineteenth-century publications have been digitized, dating the appearance of the *2nd Suppl.* is now quite straightforward: it was released by June 1875. It is listed in the [July 1 issue](#) of *The Publishers' Circular* under “New Works Published from June 16 to 30”, noted in the [July 3 issue](#) of *The Medical Times and*

¹ Brush, *Isis*, Dec. 1996, 87: 595–628

² In 1872:

- Newlands, *Chem. News J. Phys. Sci.*, 25:252 (Most hyperlinks in this article, verified in November 2025, provide access to public-domain materials hosted by Google Books and Internet Archive).
- Odling, *Proc. R. Inst. GB*, 6:386, which includes a table based on his of 1864–65.
- Odling, *Am. Chem.*, 2:424, which is a reprint of the above article (continued in [the next volume](#)).

In 1875:

- Boisbaudran, *Chem. News J. Phys. Sci.*, 32:295
- Mendeleev, *Chem. News J. Phys. Sci.*, 32:293
- Newlands, *Chem. News J. Phys. Sci.*, 31:21, which refers to [an abstract](#) of Lothar Meyer's 1873 article *On the systemization of inorganic chemistry*.

³ *The Principles of Chemistry and Molecular Mechanics*.

⁴ *Z. Chem.*, 1869, *Neue Folge* 5:405–06 (an abstract, reproduced in Fig. 1) and *Ann. Chem. Pharm., Suppl.-Bd. 8, Heft 2:133–229* (released by the end of 1871 as evidenced in [press of the time](#)).

Gazette among “Books and Pamphlets Received”, and reviewed in *Nature* in the [issue of August 26, 1875](#)—the very day before the discovery of gallium.⁵

Significant though it is, this single case does not alter Brush’s broader conclusion:

Mendeleev’s periodic law attracted little attention (at least in America and Britain) until chemists started to discover some of the elements needed to fill gaps in his table and found that their properties were remarkably similar to those he had predicted. The frequency with which the periodic law was mentioned in journals increased sharply after the discovery of gallium.⁶

In the *2nd Suppl.*, Watts devoted four pages to explaining Mendeleev’s findings *sub voce* “Elements”. He began by pointing out that Mendeleev had further developed the topic explained (by William Odling) on page 975 of the [2nd edition of volume 3](#)⁷ of his *Dictionary* and then proceeded to summarize Felix Wreden’s German translation of Mendeleev’s 1871 paper *The Periodic Law of the Chemical Elements*,⁸ from which both tables were reproduced (Figs. 3–4). Watts effectively explained Mendeleev’s key concepts, including a mention of predicting unknown elements.

Thorpe based his account of the periodic law in the 1877 edition of his manual almost verbatim on the *2nd Suppl.* He also included the two tables, fitting them onto a single page (Fig. 5). In the [1896 edition](#), however, *Watts’s Dictionary* was replaced as the source by Lothar Meyer’s [Modern Theories of Chemistry](#) (Figs. 6–7). Mendeleev remained credited for his predictions.

By 1877, the significance of the periodic law was sufficiently appreciated for questions of priority to begin to matter. In preparing the 12th edition of [Fownes’ Manual of Chemistry](#) (prefatory date February 1877, Fig. 8), Watts took a different tack. Ann Robinson observed in her analysis of this manual:

Henry Watts, who had taken over the writing of *Fownes’ Manual*, did not give sole credit to Mendeleev for the periodic law, mentioning that Newlands was the first to point out the periodic law and that it had been further developed by Odling and Mendeleev. However, the table included bears more resemblance to a Mendeleev table than to ones drawn by either Newlands or Odling [...] Watts did credit Mendeleev with the successful prediction of gallium.⁹

⁵ Boisbaudran, [Chem. News J. Phys. Sci., 32:159](#). See also Mary Elvira Weeks, *The Discovery of the Elements* (Easton, Pa.: *Journal of Chemical Education*, 1933), pp. 215–19 (1st edition).

⁶ Brush (note 1), 617. An outstanding exception is Carl Rammelsberg, who had incorporated Mendeleev’s periodic law into his German manual as early as 1872. Further details are provided in my article *Dating the First Appearance of Mendeleev’s Table in a German Textbook*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17512947](#)

⁷ Same page on [the 1st edition](#) (1865) (Fig. 2). Odling’s contributions to *Watts’s Dictionary* are thoroughly discussed in the indispensable volume *150 Years of the Periodic Table: A Commemorative Symposium* (eds. Carmen Giunta, Vera Mainz, and Gregory Girolami; Springer, 2021). DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-67910-1](#)

⁸ See note 4.

⁹ Robinson, “*Creating a Symbol of Science: The Development of a Standard Periodic Table of the Elements*” (2018). [Doctoral Dissertations 1385](#), p. 100.

In 1879, Watts maintained this claim in the [3rd Suppl.](#) to his *Dictionary*:

The idea of a periodic relation between the atomic weights of the elementary bodies and their quantivalence and other properties, developed by Mendelejeff in the manner already described ([2nd Suppl.](#) 462), was first suggested by J. R. Newlands in 1864 ([Chem. News, x. 94](#)).¹⁰

Returning to Remsen, he discussed both Mendeleev and Meyer, reproducing tables from each author (Figs. 12–14), although his exposition of Mendeleev was more extensive. From the [3rd edition of 1887](#) onward, he too added a nod to Newlands, though diplomatically:

Attention was first called to the general character of the relations between the properties of the elements and their atomic weights by J. A. R. Newlands, in a number of papers which appeared in the years 1864–66, but, owing to some marked inconsistencies in his arrangement of the elements, the importance of the subject was not generally recognized.

This matters for American history: based on Brush's lists,¹¹ Remsen's book (preface dated February 1877) was the first US publication to include Mendeleev's actual table. The Philadelphia edition (1877) of the [5th volume of Encyclopaedia Britannica](#) (9th edition) can be excluded since the table incorporated by the author of the subentry "Periodic Relations of the Elements" (Henry Armstrong) is "an alternative table to that of Mendeleev, with a space for every integral atomic weight so that there are many spaces unfilled by elements."¹²

Apart from contemporary citations such as Thorpe's, I have found only one other instance in the literature that mentions the [2nd Suppl.](#) in this context. In the 1941 article *Lewis Reeve Gibbes and the Classification of the Elements*,¹³ Wendell Taylor assessed how isolated Gibbes was from recent European advances in chemical theory, and explains that Gibbes's 1875 paper cites only a few post-1860 sources, notably the 1863 and 1868 editions of *Watts's Dictionary*. Taylor observed:

It may be noted that only in the second supplement to this (1875) did its first account of Mendeleeff's work appear, while Gibbes' principal periodical source of information, the *Chemical News*, first carried a brief account of the Periodic Law in the issue of December 24, 1875. Needless to say, no such account had yet found its way into any of the standard texts, so that the originality of Gibbes' paper can hardly be doubted.

¹⁰ *Watts's Dictionary*, 3rd Suppl., Part 1, p. 729. Newlands reproduced this passage in his vindictory [On the Discovery of the Periodic Law](#) (1884), p. 38 (Fig. 9).

¹¹ Neither Clarke, [Pop. Sci. Mo., 1876, 8:463](#) nor Baird, [Ann. Rec. Sci. Ind., 1877, p. 204](#) contains the table.

¹² Gordon Woods in *Early Responses to the Periodic System* (eds. Masanori Kaji, Helge Kragh and Gábor Palló; Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015), p. 90. Woods also discusses the prominent figure of Pattison Muir in the early acceptance of periodicity, which I leave for another article. The importance of his treatise is evidenced by copies owned by Wilhelm Ostwald and Ira Remsen (Figs. 10–11).

¹³ Taylor, [J. Chem. Educ., Sep. 1941, 18:403–407](#)

Taylor's remarks—while primarily intended to underscore Gibbes's isolation—incidentally document the *2nd Suppl.*'s early appearance, though this detail may have escaped notice in subsequent scholarship.

Early in 1871, the *Journal of the Chemical Society* began publishing the series *Abstracts of Chemical Papers Published in British and Foreign Journals*, and soon after, the revision of the abstracts was left entirely in Watts's hands. Yet Mendeleev's paper never got abstracted. The explanation might lie in priorities: dozens of papers competing for limited space.¹⁴ Nonetheless, it is only fair to acknowledge Henry Watts for introducing Mendeleev's ideas into the Anglophone scientific community—not through a journal abstract, as in the German case, but through a major reference work that was also of great use to contemporary scientists.¹⁵

If this modest finding helps fill a gap in the bibliographical record or encourages further research, it will have served its purpose.

Appendix 1: Historical authors mentioned

Henry Edward **Armstrong** (London 1848 – *ib.* 1937)
Spencer Fullerton **Baird** (Reading, PA 1823 – Falmouth, MA 1887)
Paul-Émile Lecoq de **Boisbaudran** (Cognac 1838 – Paris 1912)
Frank Wigglesworth **Clarke** (Boston, MA 1847 – Chevy Chase, MD 1931)
George **Fownes** (London 1815 – *ib.* 1849)
Lewis Reeve **Gibbes** (Charleston, SC 1810 – *ib.* 1894)
Gustavus Detlef **Hinrichs** (Lunden, Duchy of Holstein 1836 – St. Louis, MO 1923)
Raphael **Meldola** (London 1849 – *ib.* 1915)
Dmitri Ivanovich **Mendeleev** (Verkhnie Aremzyani, 1834 – St. Petersburg 1907)
Julius Lothar **Meyer** (Varel, Duchy of Oldenburg 1830 – Tübingen 1895)
Matthew Moncrieff Pattison **Muir** (Glasgow 1848 – Epsom, Surrey 1931)
John Alexander Reina **Newlands** (London 1837 – *ib.* 1898)
William **Odling** (London 1829 – Oxford 1921)
Wilhelm Friedrich **Ostwald** (Riga 1853 – Leipzig 1932)
Carl Friedrich **Rammelsberg** (Berlin 1813 – *ib.* 1899)
Ira **Remsen** (New York City, NY 1846 – Carmel, CA 1927)
Wendell Hertig **Taylor** (1905 – 1985)
Thomas Edward **Thorpe** (Manchester 1845 – Salcombe, Devon 1925)
Henry **Watts** (London 1815 – *ib.* 1884)
Mary Elvira **Weeks** (Lyons, WI 1892 – Detroit, MI 1975)
Felix Eduard Romanovich **Wreden** (Riga 1841 – St. Petersburg 1878)

¹⁴ [*Jubilee of the Chemical Society* \(1891\), pp. 243–247](#)

¹⁵ Raphael Meldola put it forcefully in his review for *Nature* (Aug. 26, 1875, 12:327–328): “The appearance of the second supplement to Watts’ ‘Dictionary of Chemistry’ is an event in the history of chemical literature which will certainly be welcomed by all English chemists [...] the ‘Dictionary’ has in fact justly taken its rank as one of the standard works of reference in this country.”

Appendix 2: Figure Captions

All images are photographs of original volumes in my collection, each with its own story to be told through all of its owners across time.

1. German abstract of Mendeleev's paper *On the relationship of the properties of the elements to their atomic weights*, published in *Zeitschrift für Chemie, Zwölfter Jahrgang, Neue Folge, V. Band, Heft 13*, Leipzig, 1869, pp. 405–406. This was the seventh appearance of the table in 1869—released ca. July 1, according to Druzhinin (2020) *The first publication of Mendeleev's periodic system of elements: a new chronology*, *Historical Studies Nat Sci* 50:129–182. This abstract was honored with the [Citation for Chemical Breakthrough Award](#) in 2012.
2. Odling's classification in *Watts's Dictionary*, vol. III (1st edition, 1865), p. 975.
3. Table I in 2nd Suppl., p. 463, corresponding to *Tabelle II* in Wreden's version (p. 151).
4. Table II in 2nd Suppl., p. 464, corresponding to *Tabelle I* in Wreden's version (p. 149).
5. Tables from figs. 3–4 reprinted in Thorpe's *Manual of Inorganic Chemistry, vol. II: The Metals* (1877 edition), p. 33.
6. Tables on p. 31 in the 1896 edition of Thorpe's *Manual of Inorganic Chemistry, vol. II: The Metals*, which is “practically a new work” (from the preface). Scandium and Germanium are now included, corresponding to Mendeleev's predictions eka-boron and eka-silicon, respectively.
7. The only English edition of Meyer's *Die modernen Theorien der Chemie* (London, 1888), translated by Peter Phillips Bedson (1853–1943) and William Carleton Williams (1850–1927).
8. Table in *Fownes' Manual of Chemistry*, Philadelphia, 1878 (American edition in one volume of the 12th British edition of 1877), p. 239.
9. Title page and binding of Newlands's *On the Discovery of the Periodic Law* (1884). This is an unsigned copy, curiously less common in the rare book market than the signed ones, as noted by Gregory Girolami in *A Book Collector's View of the Periodic Table: Key Documents before Mendeleev's Contributions of 1869* ([Substantia](#) 3(2) Suppl. 5: 109-124, 2019).
10. Table on p. 225 in Muir's *Treatise on Principles of Chemistry* (1st edition, 1884). This copy belonged to Wilhelm Ostwald—Nobel Prize in Chemistry in 1909. Scandium is included but not germanium, which had not yet been discovered.
11. Ira Remsen's copy of Muir's *Treatise on Principles of Chemistry* (2nd edition, 1889), where presumably Remsen himself underlined the passages: “We may confidently say that a large probability has been established in favour of the hypothesis [on periodicity]” (p. 223) and later: “The facts enumerated in the preceding pages undoubtedly establish the periodic law on a firm basis, and justify the employment of this law as one of the main guides in a general scheme of chemical classification” (p. 235).
12. Table I (*Tabelle I* in Wreden's translation) in Remsen's *Principles of Theoretical Chemistry* (1st edition, 1877), p. 74.
13. Table II (*Tabelle II* in Wreden's translation) in Remsen, *op. cit.*, p. 75.
14. Lothar Meyer's table in Remsen, *op. cit.*, p. 77.

Fig. 1

			Mo 96	W 184
			—	Au 196,5
			Pd 106,5	Pt 197
L 7	Na 23	—	Ag 108	—
G 9	Mg 24	Zn 65	Cd 112	Hg 200
B 11	Al 27,5	—	—	Tl 203
C 12	Si 28	—	Sn 118	Pb 207
N 14	P 31	As 75	Sb 122	Bi 210
O 16	S 32	Se 79,5	Te 129	—
F 19	Cl 33,5	Br 80	I 127	—
		K 3	Rb 85	Cs 133
		Ca 40	Sr 87,5	Ba 137
		Ti 48	Zr 89,5	—
		Cr 52,5	—	Th 231
		Mn 55 &c.	V 138	—

Fig. 2

TABLE I.

Series	Group I. R ¹	Group II. R ²	Group III. R ³	Group IV. R ⁴	Group V. R ⁵	Group VI. R ⁶	Group VII. R ⁷	Group VIII. R ⁸
1.	H = 1							
2.	Li = 7	G = 9.4	B = 11	C = 12	N = 14	O = 16	F = 19	
3.	Na = 23	Mg = 24	Al = 27.3	Si = 28	P = 31	S = 32	Cl = 35.5	
4.	K = 39	Ca = 40	-- = 44	Ti = 48	V = 51	Cr = 52	Mn = 55	Fe = 56, Co = 59 Ni = 59, Cu = 63
5.	(Cu = 63)	Zn = 65	-- = 68	-- = 72	As = 75	Se = 78	Br = 80	
6.	Rb = 85	Sr = 87	?Yt = 88	Zr = 90	Nb = 94	Mo = 96	-- = 100	Ru = 104, Rh = 104, Pd = 106, Ag = 108
7.	(Ag = 108)	Cd = 112	In = 113	Sn = 118	Sb = 122	Te = 125	J = 127	
8.	Cs = 133	Ba = 137	?Di = 138	?Ce = 140	--	--	--	
9.	(--)	--	--	--	--	--	--	
10.	--	--	?Er = 178	?La = 180	Ta = 182	W = 184	--	Os = 195, Ir = 197, Pt = 198, Au = 199
11.	(Au = 199)	Hg = 200	Tl = 204	Pb = 207	Bi = 208	--	--	
12.	--	--	--	Th = 231	--	U = 240	--	

ELEMENTS
463

Fig. 3

TABLE II.

			K = 39	Rb = 85	Cs = 133	--	--
			Ca = 40	Sr = 87	Ba = 137	--	--
			--	?Yt = 88?	?Di = 138?	Er = 178?	--
			Ti = 48?	Zr = 90	Co = 140?	?La = 180?	Th = 231
			V = 51	Nb = 94	--	Ta = 182	--
			Cr = 52	Mo = 96	--	W = 184	U = 240
			Mn = 55	--	--	--	--
			Fe = 56	Ru = 104	--	Os = 195?	--
			Co = 59	Rh = 104	--	Ir = 197	--
			Ni = 59	Pd = 106	--	Pt = 198?	--
			Cu = 63	Ag = 108	--	Au = 199?	--
			Zn = 65	Cd = 112	--	Hg = 200	--
			--	In = 113	--	Tl = 204	--
			--	Sn = 118	--	Pb = 207	--
			As = 75	Sb = 122	--	Bi = 208	--
			Se = 78	Te = 125?	--	--	--
			Br = 80	J = 127	--	--	--

Typical Elements.

H = 1	Li = 7	Na = 23
G = 9.4	Mg = 24	
B = 11	Al = 27.3	
C = 12	Si = 28	
N = 14	P = 31	
O = 16	S = 32	
F = 19	Cl = 35.5	

Fig. 4

Typical Elements.													
H = 1	Li = 7	Na = 23	K = 39	Rb = 85	Cs = 133							Th = 231	U = 240
	Gl = 9,4	Mg = 24	Ca = 40	Sr = 87	Ba = 137								
	B = 11	Al = 27,3	Ti = 48 P	Yt = 88 P	? Di = 138 P							Er = 178 P	
	C = 12	Si = 28	V = 51	Zr = 90	Ce = 140							Ta = 182	
	N = 14	P = 31	Cr = 52	Nb = 94							W = 184	
	O = 16	S = 32	Mn = 55	Mo = 96							Os = 195 P	
	F = 19	Cl = 35,5	Fe = 56	Ru = 104							Ir = 197	
			Co = 59	Rh = 104							Pt = 198 P	
			Ni = 59	Pd = 106							Au = 199 P	
			Cu = 63	Ag = 108							Hg = 200	
			Zn = 65	Cd = 112							Tl = 204	
			In = 113							Pb = 207	
			Sn = 118							Bi = 208	
			As = 75	Sb = 122	
			Se = 78	Te = 125 P	
			Br = 80	I = 127	

On re-arranging them in Series, we obtain the following Table:—

Series.	Group I. R ² O.	Group II. RO.	Group III. R ² O ₃ .	Group IV. R ⁴ O ₂ .	Group V. R ⁵ O ₃ .	Group VI. RO ₂ .	Group VII. R ² O ₇ .	Group VIII. RO ₃ .
1	H=1							
2	Li=7	Gl=9,4	B=11	C=12	N=14	O=16	F=19	
3	Na=23	Mg=24	Al=27,3	Si=28	P=31	S=32	Cl=35,5	
4	K=39	Ca=40	—=44	Ti=48	V=51	Cr=52	Mn=55	Fe=55, Co=59, Ni=59, Cu=63.
5	(Cu=63)	Zn=65	—=68	—=72	As=75	Se=78	Br=80	
6	Rb=85	Sr=87	? Yt=88	Zr=90	Nb=94	Mo=96	—=100	Ru=104, Rh=104, Pd=106, Ag=108.
7	(Ag=108)	Cd=112	In=113	Sn=118	Sb=122	Te=125	I=127	
8	Cs=133	Ba=137	? Di=138	? Ce=140	—	—	—	
9	(—)	—	? Er=178	? La=180	Ta=182	W=184	—	Os=193, Ir=197, Pt=198, Au=199.
10	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
11	(Au=199)	Hg=200	Tl=204	Pb=207	Bi=208	U=240	—	
12	—	—	—	Th=231	—	—	—	

Fig. 5

points in the series. In the following Table the elements are arranged in the order of their atomic weights:—

				K = 39.0	Rb = 85.2
				Ca = 39.9	Sr = 87.5	Yb = 173.0
				Sc = 44.0	Yt = 88.9
				Ti = 48.0	Zr = 90.4	Ce = 138.7
				V = 51.1	Nb = 93.7	Ba = 136.4	Ta = 182.0
				Cr = 52.4	Mo = 95.9	La = 138.9	W = 183.6
				Mn = 54.8	Ce = 141.2	Th = 232
				Fe = 55.9	Ru = 101.4	Os = 140.3	Os = 193.3
				Co = 58.6	Rh = 102.7	Ds = 142.6	Ir = 192.5	U = 238.8
				Ni = 58.6	Pd = 106.2	Tb = 148.7	Pt = 194.3
H = 1	Li = 7.0	Na = 23.0	Cu = 63.2	Ag = 107.6	Au = 196.8
	Be = 9.1	Mg = 23.9	Zn = 64.9	Cd = 111.7	Sm = 150	Hg = 199.8
	B = 10.9	Al = 27.0	Ga = 69.8	In = 113.4	Tl = 203.7
	C = 12.0	Si = 28.3	Ge = 72.3	Sn = 117.3	Pb = 206.4
	N = 14.0	P = 30.9	As = 74.9	Sb = 119.6	Bi = 208.4
	O = 15.9	S = 32.0	Se = 78.9	Te = 125
	F = 19.0	Cl = 35.4	Br = 79.7	I = 126.3

If now we divide the list into sections as seen below, placing the members of the 2nd under those of the 1st; those of the 3rd under those of the 2nd, and so on, we obtain the following arrangement:—

I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	VII.	VIII.		
Li	Be	B	C	N	O	F			
Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cl			
K	Ca	Sc	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni
	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	As	Se			
Rb	Sr	Yt	Zr	Nb	Mo	—	Ru	Rh	Pd
	Ag	Cd	In	Sb	Te	I			
Cs	Ba	La	Ce	D	Tb?	—	Sm?	Ir	Pt
	—	Yb	—	Ta	W	—	Os		
—	Au	Hg	Tl	Pb	Bi	—	—		
—	—	—	Th	—	U	—	—		

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Arrangement of Elements in the order of their Atomic Weights.

H 1	Li 7	Na 23	K 39	Cu 63	Rb 85	Ag 108	Cs 133	..	Au 199	..	RCl ₁
Be 9.4	Mg 24	Ca 40	Zn 65	Sr 87	Cd 112	Ba 137	..	Hg 200	..	RCl ₂	
B 11	Al 27	..	Ga 68	Y 88	In 113	Di 138	Eb 178	Tl 204	..	RCl ₃	
C 12	Si 28	Ti 48	..	Zr 90	Sn 118	Ce 140	La 180	Pb 207	Th 231	RCl ₄	
N 14	P 31	V 51	As 75	Nb 94	Sb 122	..	Ta 182	Bi 210	..	RCl ₅	
O 16	S 32	Cr 52	Se 78	Mo 96	Te 125.7	..	W 184	..	U 240	RCl ₆	
F 19	Cl 35.5	Mn 55	Br 80	..	I 127	RCl ₇	
		Fe 56	..	Ru 104	Os 195				
		Co 59	..	Rh 104	Ir 197				
		Ni 59	..	Pd 106	Pt 198				
		Cu 63				

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

To
Professor W. Ostwald

from the Author.

	GROUPS							
Series	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
	R ₂ O	R ₂ O ₂	R ₂ O ₃	R ₂ O ₄	R ₂ O ₅	R ₂ O ₆	R ₂ O ₇	[R ₂ O ₈]
1	H=1							
2	Li=7	Be=9	B=11	C=12	N=14	O=16	F=19	
3	Na=23	Mg=24	Al=27	Si=28	P=31	S=32	Cl=35.5	Fe=56 Ni=58.6
4	K=39	Ca=40	Sc=44	Ti=48	V=51	Cr=52	Mn=55	Co=59 Cu=63
5	(Cu=63)	Zn=65	Ga=69	(? 72)	As=75	Se=79	Br=80	Rh=104 Ru=104.5
6	Rb=85	Sr=87	Y=89	Zr=90	Nb=94	Mo=96	(? 100)	Pd=106 Ag=108
7	(Ag=108)	Cd=112	In=114	Sn=118	Sb=120	(? Te=126)	I=127	? 152-156 4 Elements ?
8	Cs=133	Ba=137	La=139	Ce=141	Di=144	(? 149)	? 150	
9	? 4 Elements 156 to 162 ?				Er=166	? 167	? 169	
10	? 170	? 172	Yb=173	? 178	Ta=182	W=184	? 190	Ir=192.5 Os=193
11	(Au=196)	Hg=200	Tl=204	Pb=207	Bi=209	? 2 Elements 212 to 220 ?		Pt=194 Au=196
12	? 2 Elements 220 to 230 ?			Th=232	? 237	U=240	? 245	

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

TABLE I.

		K = 39	Rb = 85	Cs = 133	—	—
		Ca = 40	Sr = 87	Ba = 137	—	—
		—	Yt = 88	Di = 138	Er = 178	—
		Tl = 48	Zr = 90	Ce = 140	La = 180	Th = 231
		V = 51	Nb = 94	—	Ta = 182	—
		Cr = 52	Mo = 96	—	W = 184	U = 240
		Mn = 55	—	—	—	—
		Fe = 56	Ru = 104	—	Os = 193	—
		Co = 59	Rh = 104	—	Ir = 197	—
		Ni = 59	Pd = 106	—	Pt = 198	—
		H = 1	Li = 7	Na = 23	Cu = 63	Ag = 108
		Be = 9.4	Mg = 24	Zn = 65	Cd = 112	Hg = 200
		B = 11	Al = 27.3	—	In = 113	—
		C = 12	Si = 28	—	Sn = 118	—
		N = 14	P = 31	As = 75	Sb = 122	—
		O = 16	S = 32	Se = 78	Te = 127	—
		F = 19	Cl = 35.5	Br = 80	I = 127	—

Typical elements.

Fig. 12

TABLE II.

Series.	Group I. R ₂ O	Group II. RO	Group III. R ₂ O ₃	Group IV. R ₂ O ₃ RO ₂	Group V. R ₂ O ₃ R ₂ O ₅	Group VI. R ₂ O ₃ RO ₂	Group VII. R ₂ O ₃ R ₂ O ₅	Group VIII. RO ₂
1	H = 1							
2	Li = 7	Be = 9.4	B = 11	C = 12	N = 14	O = 16	F = 19	
3	Na = 23	Mg = 24	Al = 27.3	Si = 28	P = 31	S = 32	Cl = 35.5	
4	K = 39	Ca = 40	— = 44	Ti = 48	V = 51	Cr = 52	Mn = 55	Fe = 56, Co = 59, Ni = 59, Cu = 63
5	(Cu = 63)	Zn = 65	— = 68	— = 72	As = 75	Se = 78	Br = 80	
6	Rb = 85	Sr = 87	? Yt = 88	Zr = 90	Nb = 94	Mo = 96	— = 100	Ru = 104, Rh = 104, Pd = 106, Ag = 105
7	(Ag = 108)	Cd = 112	In = 113	Sn = 118	Sb = 122	Te = 125	I = 127	
8	Cs = 133	Ba = 137	? Di = 138	? Ce = 140	—	—	—	
9	(—)	—	? Er = 178	? La = 180	Ta = 182	W = 184	—	
10	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	Os = 195, Ir = 197, Pt = 198, Au = 199
11	(Au = 199)	Hg = 200	Tl = 204	Pb = 207	Bi = 208	—	—	
12	—	—	—	Th = 231	—	U = 240	—	

PROPERTIES OF THE ELEMENTS.

75

Fig. 13

I.	B	C	N	O	F			H	Li	Be
II.	11.0	11.97	14.01	15.96	19.1			1	7.01	9.3
III.	Al	Si	P	S	Cl				Na	Mg
	27.3	28	30.96	31.98	35.37				22.99	23.94
IV.	? 47?	Ti	V	Cr	Mn				K	Ca
		48	51.2	52.4	54.8				39.04	39.90
V.	? 70?	? 72?	As	Se	Br	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
			74.9	78	79.75	55.9	58.6	58.6	63.3	64.9
VI.	? 88?	Zr	Nb	Mo	? 98?				Rb	Sr
		90	94	95.6					85.2	87.2
VII.	In	Su	Sb	Te	I	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ag	Cd
	113.4	117.8	122	128	126.53	103.5	104.1	106.2	107.66	111.6
VIII.	? 173?	? 178?	Ta	W	? 186?				Cs	Ba
			182	184					132.7	136.8
IX.	Tl	Pb	Bi			Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Hg
	202.7	206.4	207.5			198.6	196.7	196.7	196.2	199.8

Fig. 14